

How Important is Spatial Invariance Symmetry to Quantum Mechanics? Part II

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In Part I, we argued that if spatial translational invariance is present physically in a problem then it should appear explicitly in equations describing the situation. In particular, if an equation exists with x absent, this suggests that it is valid for any x . We suggest, however, that one should try to seek equations consistent with the x -absent equation, which show x explicitly.

In Part I, we examined the case of photon reflection, and one dimensional photon reflection-refraction. We argued that such a problem might be described in terms of probabilities which are necessarily positive, i.e. $AA/\text{velocity}$, where AA is flux. No x is present, but one may write AA as $A^*A/\text{velocity}$ and introduce $\exp(i f(x,p))$. Given that there exist exact x interaction points in the two problems and that the basic physics does not change if this x position changes, we suggested using continuity of $\exp(i f(x,p))$ and its first derivative at the x -interaction point. These two equations combined yielded a pressure balance equation which does not depend on x , suggesting that $\exp(i f(x,p)) = \exp(ipx)$, hence yielding the free particle wavefunction of quantum mechanics.

In this note, we try to consider a free particle in a somewhat different view. We do not consider any reaction at first, such as reflection or reflection-refraction. Rather, we note that the particle with constant velocity has equal probability to be in any dx region. Thus, $P(x) = dx/L$, where L is length. $P(x) > 0$, so it may be written as AA . There is x invariance in this problem and so we suggest there should be a corresponding equation(s) which yield AA , but explicitly show x . We suggest again $\exp(i f(p,x))$.

At this point, there is no interaction so there is no continuity of $\exp(i f(p,x))$ and its derivative at the interaction point. (There is no interaction point.) Instead, consider finding information about $f(p,x)$ using ideas of entropy. A particle with $P(x) = dx/L$ has equal probability to be at any x point and this suggests maximum entropy. For example, this kind of spatial probability is also used in the description of a Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) gas. We suggest that maximum entropy should also apply to $\exp(i f(p,x))$ and try to develop arguments to argue that $\exp(i f(p,x)) = \exp(ipx)$.

Finally, we consider the case of a particle in a potential $V(x)$. At first it seems that $V(x)$ does not contain spatial invariance, unlike a mirror or index of refraction-reflection junction. If, however, one considers a potential to actually be an average expression describing a set of impulse hits, then, like in an MB gas, a particle may move freely until it suffers an impulse from the potential, not another particle as in the MB gas. In such a case, one may have all p values and there is translational invariance for a free particle. Thus, $\exp(ipx)$ should hold, but this is a probability (because it is linked to the a maximum entropy solution) and so one should be able to write $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ and use this together with conservation of energy to solve the $V(x)$ problem. We consider this in more detail.

Spatial Invariance

Spatial invariance, as argued in Part I, appears in many problems. It may appear in different ways. For example, one may have a function $f(|x_1 - x_2|)$. Alternatively, one may have probabilities as in a reflection only or one dimensional reflection-refraction problem. No x

appears and one might suggest that this is due to translational invariance. Nevertheless, the mirror or n_1 - n_2 index of refraction junction physically exists at an x point which is translationally invariant. We argued in Part I that this implies that there must be x dependent equations which may combine to create a probability equation with no x present. We argued that for probability = $AA/\text{velocity}$, where AA is flux and is positive (hence the quadratic) one may use A^*A and $A=A\exp(i f(p,x))$. If one applies continuity of $A\exp(i f(p,x))$ and its first derivative at x (hence using the physical point x) one may recreate the probability equation if $f(p,x)=px$. Hence $\exp(ipx)$, the quantum free particle wavefunction emerges.

Quantum Free Particle

Here we consider a quantum free particle without any reaction, i.e. reflection or reflection-refraction. We still, however, require that there be an x related equation because there is translational invariance. $P(x)=dx/L$, where L is length is directly linked to entropy because in a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas one uses L (one dimensional gas) as proportional to the number of states.

$P(x)$ is positive and so may be written as AA . One may introduce x dependence through $AA \rightarrow A^*A$ and $A \rightarrow A\exp(i f(p,x))$. Unfortunately, one knows nothing about $f(p,x)$. We suggest that one try to deduce information about $f(p,x)$ through ideas of entropy.

$P(x)=dx/L$ suggests maximum entropy because any x point carries equal weight. We suggest that a kind of maximum entropy should also exist for $\exp(i f(p,x))$ because it is linked to $P(x)$. Thus, we maximize Shannon's entropy subject to a constraint on the first moment, i.e. x . We use i (complex i) so that the solution is periodic, i.e. linked to translational invariance:

$$\text{Maximize: } -P_1(p,x) \ln(P_1(p,x)) + i g(p) x \rightarrow P_1(p,x) = \exp(i x g(p)) \quad ((1))$$

The problem is that $g(p)$ is completely unknown. There are no continuity of $P_1(p,x)$ and its first derivative equations which when combined together yield a pressure balance type equation here as there is in the one dimensional reflection-refraction problem. The pressure in such a case was linked directly to p so $d/dx \exp(i g(p) x)$ must yield a linear p .

To proceed, we consider a scenario of $P(x)=dx/L$. In such a case, one has no idea of the value of p . Any p value could be relevant, thus all p values have equal weight. This suggests maximum entropy in p at a given x . Thus, using ((1)) for momentum leads to $P_1(p,x) = \exp(i g^2(x) p)$.

In order to have the same function apply, one may use: $\exp(ipx)$.

Thus, we suggest that $\exp(ipx)$ may emerge from a free particle scenario using the idea that translational symmetry forces the presence of x and by using maximum entropy for p and x .

The Case of a Single Quantum Bound Particle in $V(x)$

In Part I we considered reflection and one-dimensional reflection-refraction and above we considered a free particle. These examples contain spatial translational invariance, but $V(x)$

does not overtly seem to. If, however, one models $V(x)$ as a source of stochastic impulse hits which on average gives rise to an energy profile $V(x)$, it seems one may introduce spatial invariance. In particular, in an MB gas with no potential, stochastic two body hits represent impulse reactions and the particle is free otherwise. We suggest that instead of two body collisions, in a quantum bound system one has collision of a particle with virtual particles, so to speak, in the potential. Thus, a quantum particle moves freely until it suffers an impulse. This suggests translational invariance because this scenario is like the mirror or n_1 - n_2 index of refraction junction. An impulse hit may occur at any x and one may have a free p i.e. $\exp(ipx)$ at any x .

Conservation of energy, however, should still apply because nowhere was this principle violated when developing the above ideas or those in Part 1. In fact, in Part 1 energy does not change for a reflected and reflection-refracted photon or particle. Furthermore, the one dimensional-refraction-reflection problem demonstrated interference of $A\exp(ipx)+B\exp(-ipx)$ in a continuity equation and of its first derivative in a second equation. If $\exp(ipx)$ is seen as a probability, which is now justified by the entropy approach of obtaining it, then the first derivative equation from reflection-refraction:

$$P A \exp(ipx) + B (-p)\exp(ipx) \text{ at } x=x_1 \text{ junction point } ((2))$$

is also linked to an average value of p for $x < x_1$. Thus, we suggest that in the potential case, one use:

$$W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \quad a(p)\exp(ipx) \text{ where } a(p) \text{ are weights } ((3))$$

One may create an average kinetic energy that when added to $V(x)$ yields a constant energy E i.e.

$$-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W + V(x) = E_n \quad ((4))$$

$$\text{where: } -1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} = \{ \text{Sum over } p \quad a(p) p^2 / 2m \exp(ipx) \} / W \quad ((5))$$

Explicit translational invariance seems to disappear because one has $KE_{ave}(x)$ which is not translationally invariant and equals the classical value. Nevertheless, it has not really disappeared because $W(x)$ is used to calculate $P(x)$ using $W^*(x)W(x)$, just as in the $\exp(ipx)$ case. $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx) = 1$ because there is maximum entropy. Now there is no longer maximum entropy, but there is still a spatial pattern given by $W^*(x)W(x)$ which is due to $\exp(ipx)$, i.e. the manifestation of x in a translationally invariant situation.

Furthermore, one may knock out a particle with momentum p with probability $a^*(p)a(p)$ from any x point, so the idea of translational invariance is certainly physical.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we take the suggested principle from Part I that there must exist x dependent equations if spatial translation invariance appears in a problem. These equations may

sometimes follow from taking an equation with no x dependence and forcing in x . We did this for the reflection and one dimensional reflection-refraction problems in Part I. Here we consider a free particle and note that its probability is $P(x)=dx/L$, where L is length. This is associated with maximum entropy because any x has equal weight. Given that $P(x)>0$, it may be written as AA which may be generalized to A^*A with $A \rightarrow A \exp(i f(p,x))$. We suggest that the idea of maximum entropy should also apply to $\exp(i f(p,x))$ because it is derived from $P(x)=dx/L$.

Thus, we maximize $-P_1(x,p) \ln(P_1(x,p)) + i g(p)x$ (i.e. use the first moment x and i for periodicity) and find $P_1(x,p)=\exp(i g(p) x)$. Now $P(x)=dx/L$ holds for any p equally, so there should be equal probability for any p and maximum entropy in p . This suggests that $g(p)=p$ then because for a fixed x one maximizes using the first moment i.e. p . Thus, using maximum entropy arguments, together with an implicit x presence for spatial invariance, we find the quantum free particle $\exp(ipx)$.

We finally consider the case of a quantum potential $V(x)$ which does not seem to be spatially invariant. If one suggests that $V(x)$ is an average energy function and that impulse hits actually occur physically, then the particle moves at a constant p, v until it suffers an impulse hit.. Thus, spatial invariance is actually present and one may use $\exp(ipx)$. All p values, however, may appear so we suggest using $\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$. Finally, we calculate average KE using $\exp(ipx)$ as a probability, which follows from the entropic arguments. This leads to:

$$-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} + V(x) = E_n \quad \text{i.e. Schrodinger's equation.}$$